

The Effect of Self-Efficacy on Emotional Intelligence and Well-Being among Tour Guides

Jennifer Chen-Hua Min

Abstract—The concept of self-efficacy refers to people's beliefs in their ability to perform certain behaviors and cope with environmental demands. As such, self-efficacy plays a key role in linking ability to performance. Therefore, this study examines the relationships of self-efficacy, emotional intelligence (EI), and well-being among tour guides, who act as intermediaries between tourists and an unfamiliar environment and significantly influence tourists' impressions of a destination. Structural equation modeling (SEM) is used to identify the relationships between these factors. The results found that self-efficacy is positively associated with EI and well-being, and a positive link was seen between EI and well-being. This study has practical implications, as the results can facilitate the development of interventions for enhancing tour guides' EI and self-efficacy competencies, which will benefit them in terms of both enhanced achievements and improved psychological happiness and well-being.

Keywords—Self-efficacy, tour guides, tourism, emotional intelligence.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE importance of self-efficacy has received increased empirical attention in the behavior literature [1]. Bandura first developed the concept of self-efficacy as part of his social learning theory, and he defined it as one's beliefs, expectations and self-confidence regarding one's abilities to execute tasks with a certain level of performance. Self-efficacy, as the most powerful self-regulatory mechanism affecting behaviors, does not refer to a person's actual skills, but rather one's beliefs about one's potential accomplishments [2]. More specifically, self-efficacy has the power to influence individuals' self-regulatory behavior, their efforts to overcome obstacles and solve any variety of challenging situations, their feelings of stress and anxiety, and their performance and coping behavior. Bandura further argues that self-efficacy is the chief construct linking ability to performance [3]. Those with high self-efficacy believe in "their capabilities to mobilize the motivation, cognitive resources, and courses of action needed to meet given situational demands" [4, p. 408], resulting in greater confidence in successfully completing a task. Moreover, those with high self-efficacy tend to put forth more effort and persistence, recover more quickly, and maintain commitments to goals better than those with low self-efficacy.

The concept of EI has attracted the attention of both academic scholars and practitioners in the past two decades. In areas such as psychology, education, and management, an

increasing body of research has focused on the study of emotions. Subsequently, studies in the area of organizational behavior have also begun giving increased attention to the relationship between emotions and actions [5]. The research to date has shown a clear relationship between emotions and self-efficacy. Emotions motivate and energize actions, they control and regulate actions, and they facilitate the assessing and implementing of specific goals or tasks [6]. Thus, the ability to recognize, express, motivate, regulate, control and manage one's own emotions and those of others is a useful skill for all people. According to [7], emotions may have an effect on how people make decisions, solve problems, interact with others, and use creativity in work settings. The use of emotions in these areas is consistent with the behaviors related to self-efficacy. EI, a term first coined by Salovey and Mayer in 1990 [8, p. 189], is described as "the ability to monitor one's own and others' feelings and emotions, to discriminate among them and to use this information to guide one's thinking and actions". Furthermore, Mayer and Salovey [9] explain EI as the ability to perceive emotions, assimilate feelings related to emotions, understand what emotions mean, and manage emotions effectively. In this view, EI can be seen as a set of abilities that relate closely to motivation.

Considerable research in recent decades indicates that people with high EI skills tend to have positive outlooks due to their abilities to reorganize thoughts and emotions productively during times of stress, which helps them adapt to challenging situations, solve problems more effectively, and act with optimism and confidence [10]. These characteristics of EI comprise a sense of self-efficacy, which enables people to successfully engage and complete a task. Numerous studies provide evidence that, in the workplace, EI skills are critical in enhancing the efficacy and productivity of employees, which in turn leads to greater commitment and thus increased efficiency in the organization [11], [12].

Previous research examining happiness and its predictors has been important at understanding the factors that lead to optimal psychological functioning. In empirical studies, happiness is often characterized as subjective well-being (SWB) [13]. Studies have shown that associations exist between well-being and self-efficacy. For instance, Priesack and Alcock [14] argue that those with higher self-efficacy will be more likely to be better at coping with stress, which results in enhancement of achievements and psychological happiness and well-being. Researchers in the management field are also now embracing the concept of EI due to recognition of its applicability to issues such as life satisfaction and well-beings. In a recent meta-analysis study focusing on the relationship between EI

Jennifer Chen-Hua Min (Professor) is with the Department of International Business, Ming Chuan University, No.250, Sec. 5, Zhongshan N. Rd., Taipei 11103, Taiwan, R.O.C. (e-mail: jennifer_min.tw@yahoo.com.tw).

and SWB, the researchers found evidence of a positive significant relationship between EI and SWB [15].

In sum, both self-efficacy and EI are significant determinants of well-being. The positive impact of EI on self-efficacy was also supported through the empirical examinations.

A. Problem Statement and Purpose of the Study

Despite proven hypotheses confirming the relationships between EI, self-efficacy, and well-being, there is not, as yet, enough interest in the topic among tourism scholars. Goleman [16] argues that customer service providers with EI skills are very adept at influencing positive responses in the people with whom they interact. It has further been argued that human service occupations, which require high levels of personal interaction, are linked with the experience of emotions and greater levels of stress than other occupations [17]. As an industry, the tourism industry is considered a typical service industry, one that involves high-contact encounters and significant interaction among customers, staff, and facilities. Serving and satisfying customers are fundamental goals of the tourism business, with service providers being part of the product itself [18]. Moreover, the labor-intensive nature of the tourism industry means that its success depends heavily on employees' performance and self-efficacy [19]. The competencies of EI and self-efficacy thus seem to be needed for people working in the tourism industry

Tour guides are the front-line service providers in the tourism industry. By introducing tourists to new environments, they influence how tourists see a host destination and therefore greatly determine the overall success of a tour experience [10], [18], [20]. Tourists' affective responses are shaped strongly by the performance of tour guides, and these responses in turn influence encounter-level satisfaction [18]. In addition, tour guides must be able to control their emotions and interact with others well, as their job involves high-contact encounters and frequent interaction with tourists [21]. In addition, because of the nature of the occupational group in which tour guides face tourists with their countenance and a great deal of interaction with the visitors, their positive psychology, such as self-efficacy, acts as an important element that can influence their performance [22], [23].

Numerous studies have identified that the competencies of EI can be learned and enhanced through proper training techniques [24], [10]. In addition, research has suggested that self-efficacy can also be learned [25]. Once learned, the abilities of EI and self-efficacy can be improved, which in turn allows an individual to become more confident in successfully completing tasks when faced with challenging situations, resulting in an increase in one's positive mind set and well-being. Surprisingly, however, the relationships of EI, self-efficacy, and well-being among the tour guide population have received relatively little discussion in the tourism literature. It is worthwhile to examine how these relationships affect tour guides due to the significant role they play in the success or failure of a tour experience and in influencing tourists' perceptions of the host destination. Therefore, this study examines these relationships using self-evaluation, with

the goal of achieving a better understanding of how these three factors interact among guide groups. SEM, a type of multivariate analysis, is used to identify significant relationships between these factors, as this allows for the simultaneous estimation of multiple regressions to confirm the theoretically built model. These results have practical implications, as they can help with the development of interventions aimed at improving tour guides' EI and self-efficacy competencies, which can ultimately benefit them in both enhancement of achievements and psychological happiness and well-being.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The literature review section describes the inbound tourism industry and tour guides in Taiwan, and research hypotheses in the current study.

A. The Inbound Tourism Industry and Tour Guides in Taiwan

Tourism is important for many countries. Destinations rely on tourism due to the income it generates in the form of money spent by tourists and taxes levied on business in the tourism industry, as well as the opportunities for employment it provides in the service industries associated with tourism. In particular, tourism is considered as a labor intensive industry. For Taiwan, tourism is one of the major service sectors, and the government has implemented policies to improve inbound tourism, such as "Doubling Tourists Arrival Plan 2008" in 2002, "Project Vanguard for Excellence in Tourism" in 2009, "Taiwan - the Heart of Asia" for the country's centennial celebrations (the year of 2011), and "Applying Diverse Promotions to Develop Markets Around the World" in 2014. In addition, Taiwan's Tourism Bureau has proposed "Taiwan's 2015-2018 Tourism Action Plan", which is aimed at "optimizing both quality and quantity" and will be implemented with "high quality, uniqueness, wisdom, and sustainability" to improve the island's competitiveness in international tourism [26]. The results of attempts to promote this industry have been successful. Both the numbers of international arrivals and foreign currency receipts have seen a steady increase. Fig. 1 illustrates the increasing inbound volume and tourism receipts over the recent decade (2001-2015). With the exception of the period surrounding the 2003 SARS epidemic and a slight dip in tourism receipts in 2015, as shown in Fig. 1, there has been an overall upward trend in both the inbound visitors and receipts in Taiwan.

Given the increase in inbound tourists, tour guides are now seen as playing an increasingly important role for Taiwan's international tourism, as their performance influences the success or failure of a tour experience, and even the perception of tourists regarding the host destination. Because tour guides have such responsibility for the overall satisfaction and impressions of tourists, the *Ministry of Examination* in Taiwan has held an annual examination of tour guides since 2004. As mentioned, the Taiwanese government has made many efforts in recent years to develop a more diverse travel environment and enhance competition to attract more inbound tourists. As a result of the efforts, the tour guide demand has greatly

increased. In order to resolve the shortage of guide personnel in Taiwan, the requirements were extended to graduates of high schools and vocational schools. After the graduates passed the tests, they underwent pre-employment training provided by the Tourism Bureau, they received a certificate of course completion, and they then applied for professional certification.

Seeing a lucrative business opportunity, over 25,000 people registered to take the annual tour guide license examination in recent years. Fig. 2 illustrates the increasing volume of tour guides from 1980 to 2015, which represents an increase of more than 30-fold [26].

Fig. 1 Inbound volume and tourism receipts of Taiwan, 2001-2015

Fig. 2 Number of tour guides, 1980-2015

B. Research Hypotheses

Considerable evidence supports the notion of a significant and positive relationship between EI and self-efficacy in organizational and academic settings. Walter et al., for example, assessed the academic self-efficacy of students at risk for attrition in higher education while they were participating in short-term intervention discipline courses [27]. The results found that the courses promoted the development of EI, improved the students' academic self-efficacy, and enhanced their ability to employ coping strategies in a way to reduce these students' attrition rates. Jiang [6] did a study of

undergraduate students in northern central China and found EI to be a predictor of career decision-making self-efficacy. One study, conducted by [12], examined the relationship between EI and self-efficacy with demographic variables in a motor company; the results showed that there was a positively significant relationship between EI and self-efficacy. Assessments have also been extended to investigate the relationships among teacher populations [11], [28]. For instance, Chan [11] examined the role of perceived EI and self-efficacy toward helping others among secondary school teachers and found EI as the significant predictor in predicting

self-efficacy toward helping others. A study by [29] examined tour guides' burnout from the perspectives of psychological empowerment; their finding that self-efficacy has a significant positive effect on EI differed from previous research, though it should be noted that their study lacked a literature review.

Some studies have examined the influence of both EI and self-efficacy on job performances or demographic variables, such as [30] for academic achievement, [5] for commitment to the teaching profession, and [31] on gender differences for creative professionals. However, there have not been any investigations of the relationship specifically between EI and self-efficacy, which is a gap that this study aims to fill. Accordingly, the hypothesis is proposed:

Hypothesis 1. Tour guides' EI will be positively related to self-efficacy.

As aforementioned, self-efficacy refers to one's belief in one's ability to successfully execute a certain course of behavior or cope with environmental demands. In order to understand how self-efficacy relates to well-being, it is important to understand the psychological mechanisms that may explain this relationship. Self-efficacy is linked to task-specific capability, and individuals with high self-efficacy are therefore able to set high goals, put forth greater effort, and perform more effectively, resulting in successful outcomes and increased well-being. Evidence indicates that self-efficacy is known to be a resource that contributes to well-being, resilience, and academic achievement, and it is therefore a relevant topic for investigation. For instance, a significant positive correlation was found between psychological well-being and self-efficacy among nurse students in a study conducted by [14]. In light of the weight of the empirical evidence, the hypothesis is proposed:

Hypothesis 2. Tour guides' self-efficacy will be positively related to well-being.

In recent years, there has been growing interest in the issue of how people process emotionally relevant information. Processing this information in an efficient and accurate manner can allow people to achieve success at work and improve their general well-being [32]. For instance, Pau and Croucher [33] found that individuals with high EI tended to have less perceived stress and better health and well-being. One study by [13], conducted with 267 participants sampled from the general population, provides new insights into EI as a predictor of SWB. Reference [34] supported these findings by demonstrating that EI leads to job satisfaction and well-being, with positive path associations leading to employee engagement and organizational commitment, thereby affecting turnover intentions among police officers in Australia. Moreover, a meta-analysis by [15] examined a total of 25 studies with 77 effect sizes and a combined sample of 8,520 participants, with the finding that a positive significant relationship exists between EI and SWB. Therefore, based on the empirical evidence, the hypothesis is proposed:

Hypothesis 3. Tour guides' EI will be positively related to well-being.

In the present study, self-efficacy will be further explored in terms of its probable mediating role in the relationship between

EI and well-being. Therefore, the hypothesis is formulated:
Hypothesis 4. Tour guides' self-efficacy plays an important role as a mediating factor in the relationships between EI and well-being.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Instruments

The present study involves the collection and analysis of quantitative data in order to explore the relationships among self-efficacy, EI, and well-being among the tour guide population. Three self-report instruments using a 5-point Likert scale were adopted in the study to assess the links of these three variables. The measurements include Wong and Law's Emotional Intelligence Scale (WLEIS) [35], the Chinese version of the General Self-Efficacy Scale developed by [36], and the short version of Chinese Happiness Inventory [37]. The demographic questions, including social demographics (e.g. gender, age, education, and marital status) and work variables (e.g. primary languages used and work experience) are also included. Before conducting the current study, it was reviewed and approved by the Institutional Review Board (IRB). The study now meets the requirements of the IRB, one of which requires that all participants of the study should be aged 20 and above.

The WLEIS scale developed by Wong and Law is consistent with Mayer and Salovey's definition of EI [9], [35]. Previous studies support the scale's factor structure, internal consistency, and convergent and discriminant validity when used for the Chinese population, which lends support to its feasibility as a research instrument to measure EI appropriately in the current study [35]. The scale, which consists of four dimensions containing four items each, aims to tap individuals' knowledge about their own emotional capacities. The dimensions included in this scale are Self-Emotion Appraisal (SEA), Others' Emotion Appraisal (OEA), Regulation of Emotion (ROE), and Use of Emotion (UOE).

In the present study, general self-efficacy was measured by the Chinese version of the General Self-efficacy Scale (GSES). The GSES consists of 10 items, and a higher score indicates a higher level of general self-efficacy [36]. It has also been adapted to the Chinese population with good reliability and validity. The subjective factor of "well-being" was adopted by the Chinese Happiness Inventory (CHI) to assess perceived level of happiness. These 10 items' scores represent the respondents' feelings of SWB, and a high score indicated high levels of well-being [37].

With regard to the applicability of each item to the current study, interviews were conducted to collect seven expert opinions: one governmental officer, one senior tour guide with over 20 years of experience, and five university professors in the field of tourism management. Two specific questions were asked of the tourism professionals: (1) Are there any modifications in terms of wording that should be made to fit the guide profession? (2) Are there any details that should be eliminated or added to items to make them more applicable to evaluate the tour guides? Expert opinions were collected,

common agreements were reached, and revisions were made in order to make items applicable to tour guide characteristics. Prior to the survey, a pilot test had been conducted to assess the reliability of the attributes and to ensure that the wording of the questionnaire was clear. Thirty tour guides were asked to complete the scale in a pilot test and note any unclear elements before it was finalized. The results showed that the Cronbach's α coefficients of EI, self-efficacy, and well-being were 0.927, 0.913, and 0.927 respectively, which means they were internally consistent and reliable.

B. Procedure and Sample Characteristics

Seeing as the majority of these tour guides (78%) work on a freelance basis, we sought the cooperation of the Taiwan Tourist Guide Association, which determined that they could benefit from the findings and thus agreed to assist with the research. Upon completion of the questionnaires, every respondent was given a gift, in an effort to increase the overall response rate. The questionnaire consisted of three parts: a cover letter, the three measurement instruments, and the demographic questions. The cover letter explained the reason for conducting the research, as well as how the data would be used and who would be able to access the data. In total, 500 surveys were distributed to tour guides, and due to the generous support of the Taiwan Tourist Guide Association, 434 surveys were returned. After accounting for invalid questionnaires ($n=21$), a total of 413 individuals who completed all items were included for analysis, yielding an effective response rate of 82.6%.

The profiles of the respondents are shown in Table I. Of the usable cases, there were 234 males (56.7%) and 179 females (43.3%), which reflects the gender proportions of Taiwan's tour guide population (59%: 41%) as reported in 2016 [26]. Most respondents' were over 40 years old (81.6%), and more than half of the respondents (70.7%) had graduated from university (47.9% from an undergraduate programme; 22.8% from a postgraduate programme). Regarding marital status, 63.9% were married, 32.7% were single, and 3.4% were divorced or widowed. The majority (62.3%) of respondents had less than 10 years of experience working as tour guides. Mandarin Chinese was the language used by most of the respondents (70.7%), while fifty-five tour guides (13.3%) indicated that they used more than one language.

IV. EMPIRICAL RESULTS

The collected data were analysed using SPSS 20.0 and SmartPLS 3.2.4 for Windows. The reliability coefficients, means, standard deviations, and the intercorrelations amongst the various measures and the subscales are shown in Table II. The Cronbach's alphas, ranging from 0.818 to 0.911, indicate that internal consistency exists. In terms of intercorrelations, there were significant correlations amongst all the scales and subscales. Table II also revealed, as expected, that tour guides' EI was positively and significantly related to self-efficacy and SWB, while tour guides' self-efficacy was significantly positively related to well-being.

TABLE I
 DEMOGRAPHIC PROFILE OF RESPONDENTS

	Frequency ($N=413$)	%
<i>Gender</i>		
male	234	56.7
female	179	43.3
<i>Age group</i>		
20~29 years	28	6.8
30~39 years	48	11.6
40~49 years	99	24.0
50~59 years	171	41.4
60 years and above	67	16.2
<i>Education</i>		
vocational school	33	8.0
college	88	21.3
university	198	47.9
postgraduate	94	22.8
<i>Marital status</i>		
single	264	63.9
married	135	32.7
divorced or widowed	14	3.4
<i>Language</i>		
Chinese	293	70.7
English	39	9.4
Japanese	13	3.1
others	14	3.4
more than one language	55	13.3
<i>Work experience</i>		
under 1 years	71	17.2
1-9 years	269	65.1
10-19 years	51	12.3
20-29 years	13	3.1
30-39 years	6	1.5
40 years above	3	0.7

A. Assessment of Measurement Model

The indicators of goodness of fit are comparative fit index (CFI) = 0.970, normed fit index (NFI) = 0.952, Tucker Lewis index (TLI) = 0.962 (acceptably ≥ 0.90) and root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA) = 0.064 (acceptably ≤ 0.08). Based on the results, all of the model-fit indices exceeded the common acceptance levels, thus demonstrating that the hypothesized model fits the empirical data well.

The measurement model was further evaluated in terms of reliability, convergent validity, and discriminant validity after achieving adequate overall fit indices (see Table III). All items were loaded at least 0.5 on their assigned factors, and all loadings were statistically significant, indicating a satisfactory estimation for item reliability. In addition to the internal consistency on Cronbach's alpha coefficients of 0.842, 0.911, and 0.892 in each of the dimensions respectively shown in Table II, construct reliability (CR) describes the shared variance among a set of observed variables measuring an underlying construct. Table III shows that the CR was above the suggested criterion of 0.70, demonstrating high reliability for all the constructs. The average variance extracted (AVE) used to assess convergent validity represents the overall amount of variance in the indicators captured by the latent construct. Satisfactory evidence for convergent validity was provided

because each AVE value exceeded the threshold values of 0.5 (0.548).

B. Assessment of Structural Model and Hypotheses Testing

The present study tested three hypotheses through SEM in the developed research model. The structural paths were estimated to examine the hypothesised relationships among

independent and dependent variables, graphically displayed as Fig. 3. The observed variables are enclosed in squares, and the latent variables are enclosed in circles. A one-way path between constructs is indicative of a hypothesised direct effect of one construct on another.

TABLE II
 PEARSON CORRELATION, MEANS, STANDARD DEVIATIONS, AND CRONBACH'S ALPHA RELIABILITY AMONG MODEL VARIABLES

	EI	SEA	ROE	UOE	OEA	SE	WB	Cronbach's Alpha
EI	1.000	0.694**	0.772**	0.752**	0.732**	0.690**	0.508**	0.842
SEA		1.000	0.432**	0.333**	0.403**	0.481**	0.350**	0.868
ROE			1.000	0.397**	0.464**	0.536**	0.359**	0.818
UOE				1.000	0.351**	0.474**	0.483**	0.880
OEA					1.000	0.558**	0.410**	0.904
SE						1.000	0.519**	0.911
WB							1.000	0.892
Mean	4.051	4.179	3.890	4.143	3.991	3.985	4.008	
SD	0.449	0.509	0.609	0.744	0.570	0.496	0.552	

Note: SE, Self-efficacy; WB, Well-being. * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$

TABLE III
 MEASUREMENT MODEL RESULTS

Construct	Variables	Standardised loadings	Item reliability	t-Value	SE	CR	AVE
EI	SEA	0.686	0.844	n/a	n/a	0.829	0.548
	ROE	0.779	0.868	5.342***	0.042		
	UOE	0.639	0.839	3.104**	0.033		
	OEA	0.652	0.895	4.603***	0.044		
SE	SE	0.572	0.939	n/a	n/a	-	-
WB	WB	0.455	0.794	n/a	n/a	1	1

a $CR = (\sum \text{Standardized loadings})^2 / [(\sum \text{Standardized loadings})^2 + \sum C_j]$, b $AVE = \sum (\text{Standardized loadings})^2 / [\sum (\text{standardized loadings})^2 + \sum C_j]$, where C_j is the measurement error, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$

Fig. 3 Results of SEM

Within the overall model, the estimates of the structural coefficients provide the basis for testing the proposed hypotheses. Table IV reports the results of the hypothesis tests, and all paths in the model were significant. The findings fully supported the hypotheses, and these findings are consistent with the results in previous studies.

Previous empirical research has suggested a direct relationship between EI, self-efficacy, and well-being. Therefore, for the purpose of ruling out the possibility of such

direct effects, the mediating effect of self-efficacy was further assessed by analyzing the indirect effect of EI on well-being. The results showed that the mediating effect of self-efficacy between EI and well-being reaches 0.223 of the multiplication of two coefficients (0.694 x 0.321 = 0.223), which is less than the direct impact of EI on well-being (0.285). Interestingly, although not previously tested in the literature, these findings indicate that self-efficacy plays a partial mediating role in the relationship between EI and well-being. Hypothesis 4 was

therefore supported. However, despite this partial mediating role of self-efficacy, the fact that the paths from EI to self-efficacy and from self-efficacy to well-being both turn out as significant indicates that self-efficacy itself can lead to better well-being and justifies its own contribution. The indirect effect is therefore recognized. Table V summarises the measured effects of all relationships.

TABLE IV
SUMMARY OF HYPOTHESIS TESTING RESULTS

Path	Structural coefficients	SE	t-Value	Test result
EI→ SE	0.694	0.031	22.085***	Support
SE →WB	0.321	0.075	4.286***	Support
EI→WB	0.285	0.072	3.952***	Support

* $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$

TABLE V
DIRECT, INDIRECT AND TOTAL EFFECTS OF RELATIONSHIPS

Path	Direct effect	Indirect effect	Total effect
EI→ SE	0.694	-	0.694
SE →WB	0.321	-	0.321
EI→WB	0.285	0.223	0.508

V. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Self-efficacy refers to people's beliefs about their ability to perform certain behaviors or deal with environmental demands. As such, it can be seen as the chief construct linking ability to performance. While there is considerable evidence of the importance of self-efficacy, and while its relationships with various work and life related factors have been acknowledged, there is currently a lack of research in the tourism literature examining its predictors and consequences among the tour guide population, who significantly influence tourists' impressions of a destination. The aim of this study is thus to explore the relationships of self-efficacy on EI and well-being. The study further aims to determine if self-efficacy is a mediator in the relationships between EI and well-being. The obtained results indicated that self-efficacy and EI were positively correlated with well-being; tour guides with higher self-efficacy and EI levels reported being more happy. In addition, a significant link was seen between self-efficacy and EI, as tour guides with high EI experienced better self-efficacy. The results are consistent with previous research showing these relationships for other settings.

The findings from the SEM also suggested that the relatively stronger correlation between EI and self-efficacy ($r = 0.694$) was found in comparison to EI-well-being ($r = 0.285$) and self-efficacy-well-being ($r = 0.321$), indicating that tour guides' EI is more predictive of tour guides' self-efficacy. In this study, an additional step was taken to estimate the mediating role of self-efficacy between EI and SWB. The results indicated that self-efficacy plays a partial mediating role in the relationship, and its indirect effect also exists. To our knowledge, the present study is the first to examine the effect of these relationships, and these findings contribute to existing tourism literature by indicating what levels of EI, self-efficacy, and well-being tour guides currently possess. This allows for a clearer understanding of the relationships between these factors

among the tour guide population.

Tour guides play an important role in the tourism industry, as they significantly influence tourists' perception of the host destination. Consequently, it is important to devise a strategy for increasing tour guides' competencies of self-efficacy and EI. Past research has shown that the employees can benefit from self-efficacy and EI interventions [25]. Self-efficacy and EI abilities can be learned and improved, which allows individuals to become more confident in dealing with challenging situations. The result of such improvements is an increase in one's well-being.

It is important to note the limitations of the present results. Regarding the data collection, this study used a survey with data collected at a single point in time, and as a result it was unable to measure potential changes in participants over time. A longitudinal study would thus contribute to the body of research concerning the relationships between self-efficacy, EI, and well-being among tour guides. Furthermore, it would be worthwhile to conduct in-depth explorations with qualitative interviews, as this could lead to a better understanding of tour guides' self-efficacy in general and their happy status in particular.

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Jennifer Chen-Hua Min received her Ph.D. degree in Institute of Business & Management, National Chiao Tung University, Taiwan, in 2001. She is a Professor in the International Business Department of Ming Chuan University, Taipei, Taiwan. Her research focuses have been emotional intelligence (EI) training, education for personnel, tourism flows analysis, emotional management programs, and related subjects.